

**RAYAT-BAHRA
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EURO-ASIAN CONFERENCE

ON

Sustainable Nanotechnology, Environment, & Energy (SNE2-2024)

Organized by

**Research & Incubation Centre
Rayat Bahra University, Mohali, Punjab, India**

in association with

**National University of Singapore, University of Salento, Italy &
University of Montpellier, France**

Join us

 15th - 16th October, 2024

HYBRID MODE

Contact us

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EURO-ASIA CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE NANOTECHNOLOGY, ENVIRONMENT, AND ENERGY (SNE2-2024)

Instructions

1. The presenter's allotted time for presentation is 10 min with 2 mins of Q & A.
2. The audience to keep their cams and audio off. Also, any question from the audience is typed into the classroom chat which will be taken up by the session chair to the presenter after the presentation.
3. All presenters within the time slot i.e., before lunch or post-lunch to be available online as anyone can be called upon for presentation to avoid unnecessary delays.
4. The session chair will indicate the presenter using an alarm (Use mobile alarm) through AUDIO regarding the presentation time left (at 8 mins) without interrupting the presenter.
5. All decisions of the session lie within the jurisdiction of the session chairs.

Technical Session 1 (DAY-1); October 15th, 2024

Keynote Speaker : Prof. (Dr) Volker Hessel; The University of Adelaide, Australia

Session Chair: Dr. Belgin SEVER ; Anadolu University Turkey

Zoom Meeting Link:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/89869315547?pwd=Zo3nFmWCvpBHdDGf26omsodzN50zwz.1>

Meeting ID: 898 6931 5547 ; Passcode: 200965

Keynote Speaker 11:30 PM to 12:00 PM;

S. No.	Presenter Name	Paper Title	SLOT	Timing (IST)
1.	Sonali Goyal	Efficient Desulfurization of Light Crude Oil Using MOF and its composite.	Post-Lunch	12:00-12:10 pm
2.	DuÅ¼ica JovanoviÄ	ZnO-based coatings in solar-enhanced removal of ciprofloxacin from the aqueous medium		12:10-12:20 pm
3.	Paolo Pellegrino	Antibacterial Properties of PMMA Nanograting and Nanopillar Arrays: An AFM Analysis		12:20-12:30 pm
4.	Szabolcs BognÄr	Advancing sustainable nanotechnology: Green synthesis of ZnO nanomaterials for photocatalytic degradation of organics in water		12:30-12:40 pm
5.	Subham Chakraborty	Measuring of Surface Roughness of Al-6061 Alloy by CNC Milling by using of Taguchi Method		12:40-12:50 pm
6.	Laura Maria Slavu	Bimetal nanoparticles based Cu@Au nanozyme as promising nanomaterials for enhanced sensitive lateral flow assay (LFAs)		12:50-01:00 pm
7.	Anu Radha Pathania	Comparative analysis of glimepiride interactions with bovine serum albumin and fibrinogen using fluorescence spectroscopy		01:00-01:10 pm
8.	Annalisa Bianco	Green synthesis of Chitosan Nanoparticles as Locked Nucleic Acid Delivery Systems		01:10-01:20 pm
9.	Batchu Ramanajneyulu	Transforming Treacherous Terrains: Enhancing Black Cotton Soil Stability with Calcium Lignosulfonate and Marble Dust		01:20-01:30 pm
10.	Sajal Rai	Investigations on melt flow index of orange peel powder reinforced thermoplastic composites for fdm filament fabrication		01:30-01:40 pm

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ZnO-based coatings in solar-enhanced removal of ciprofloxacin from the aqueous medium

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Abstract. Environmental pollution is rising and causing serious, irreversible harm to the world. Water pollution, in particular, stands out as a major global issue as all living beings rely on natural water sources. Pharmaceuticals, particularly antibiotics, contribute to environmental pollution and pose risks to aquatic ecosystems even at low concentrations. Namely, misuse of these substances can promote antibiotic-resistant bacteria, highlighting the need for careful monitoring. Heterogeneous photocatalysis offers an environmentally friendly and sustainable method for eliminating organic pollutants. By utilising light and a catalyst, this process generates reactive species that play a key role in the removal of persistent organics. A novel approach to water remediation technologies is the development of photocatalysts in the form of coatings. Unlike traditional powder-based photocatalysts, coatings offer uniform coverage, reduced handling complexity, and a broader range of applications. For this study, two novel green ZnO-based nanopowders, synthesised using plant extracts of banana peel and green tea, were immobilised on the alumina plates using a screen-printing technique. The photocatalytic activity of the obtained ZnO-based coatings was assessed in the solar-enhanced removal of ciprofloxacin, a fluoroquinolone antibiotic, from a river water matrix. Additionally, the reusability of the coatings was tested in three consecutive runs.

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This is to Certify that Mr./Ms. Dusica Jovanovia from University of Novi Sad Faculty of Sciences, Serbia has presented a paper entitled "ZnO-based coatings in solar-enhanced removal of ciprofloxacin from the aqueous medium" at "EURO-ASIAN CONFERENCE ON SUSTAINABLE NANOTECHNOLOGY, ENVIRONMENT & ENERGY (SNEE-2024)" Organized by Research & Incubation Centre, Rayat Bahra University, Punjab, India in association with the National University of Singapore, University of Salento, Italy & University of Montpellier, France on **15 -16th October 2024.**

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